

THE ROLE OF THE FAMILY IN FORMING THE PATRIOTIC SENSE OF THE YOUTH IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. The article presents opinions and recommendations on the role of the family in society, its duties, definitions, parental responsibility in raising children in the family, the concept of the Motherland, military-patriotic feeling and ways of its formation in the mind. the youth.

Key words: Family, society, motherhood, children, upbringing, Motherland, military patriotism, morality, example, heroism, devotion, courage.

Family is the basis of society. Due to the fact that the family and its environment occupy a necessary place in the development of society, starting from the first years of production and up to this day, family issues are strictly controlled in our republic. Moreover, It is noteworthy that a separate chapter of the Constitution, which is our main encyclical, is devoted to family and family relations. Since the family is the main link of the society, it is under the protection of the society and the state in our country. According to official publications: Family is a group of people living together, consisting of a couple, their children and the closest relatives. A family is a small group based on marriage or birth. Its members are bound together by unity of livelihood, mutual aid and moral responsibility. [1].

A family is formed on the basis of warm relations between two people, that is, a boy and a girl, a man and a woman. As a symbol of this relationship, a child is born and serves as a nation that preserves the family. The main social task of the family is to give birth and raise a person. Education is a multifaceted process that ensures the development of a person. The idea of raising a perfect person is considered an urgent issue in all times. A mentally mature, morally pure and physically healthy person is considered a bright image of a perfect person. These qualities are closely related and complement each other.

Many works have been written dedicated to human morality and spirituality. In this regard, large-scale research is still being carried out. But it is worth noting that in the moral education of a person, we cannot do without focusing on the family. Because the family is the primary factor in the process of human socialization, formation and development as a person. Father and mother have equal responsibility in raising a child. Mutual relations of family members are determined by existing social, economic and ideological relations in society. But this situation does not deny

that parents are responsible for the education of their children. According to our traditions, a child is considered a deposit in the hands of his parents.

For this reason, it is the duty of every parent to bring up sons and daughters with good character and profession, to try to embody human qualities in them. There are many valuable ideas in our national spiritual heritage about the role of parents in the strength of the family and the upbringing of children.

Studying them and using their achievements has a positive effect on the effectiveness of the pedagogical process. The famous scholar Yusuf Khos Khajib in his work "Kutadgu Bilig" stated: "If a father leaves a child bereft when he is young, there is no sin in the child, all the suffering is on the father himself. If the boy's behavior is naughty, then the father has done this naughty thing. If the father supervises the children and teaches them various trades, when they grow up, he will be happy that he has sons and daughters." [2].

According to the opinion of the encyclopedist Abu Ali Ibn Sina: "If the head of the family is inexperienced and incompetent, he will not be able to educate the family members well, and as a result, bad results may occur." [3]. "A good wife is the state and happiness of the family," said Hazrat Alisher Navoi in his works. [4]. In fact, the service of a woman is great in the strengthening of the family and in the education of children. Because, compared to the father, the mother communicates more with her children. Communication is one of the main factors in human development. Sometimes, for various reasons, children remain in the hands of only one mother or father, and certain difficulties arise in the family in raising children. At this point, the thoughts of Abu Bakr Muhammad al-Khorazmi come to mind.

He divides the parents and gives a definition. The first are physical, i.e. those who cause the birth of a child, and the second - spiritual, mainly, those who teach [5]. According to Thinker, in cases where the parents have limited opportunities, it is necessary to involve experienced specialist teachers and trainers in child education. "Physically unhealthy," says M. Inomova, doctor of pedagogy, "it is very difficult to bring up a child born to a person who has no family history, is morally corrupt, and is spiritually poor." [6]. The scientist, in this place, draws our attention to the natural and hereditary factors that directly affect the development of the individual. In fact, some people do not take care of their health with the wise idea that "healthy parents give birth to a healthy child". It's a pity, of course. As our great-grandfathers said, "Spirituality is nurtured by mother's milk, father's example, and ancestors' fertilizer."

These words have a great meaning. The child directly accepts the words and actions of his parents without critical observation. Unaware of this, some parents try to call their children to the right path while being immoral themselves. It should always be remembered that father and mother are role models for children in every field. Homeland is as sacred as a place of worship. His protection is a sacred duty.

It is coincidence that Article 52 of our Constitution of states: "Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the duty of every citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan." The concept of "Motherland" has been a sacred and supreme value for our people since ancient times. Therefore, special attention is paid to it in our national spiritual heritage. If we pay attention to the history of the origin of this magical word, we will see that it is formed on the basis of the Arabic verb - [watana], which means "to live", "to live".

Therefore, "homeland" serves to ensure the right of a person to live. The life of a person who has a homeland will be full, all his dreams will come true. A person strives to fully demonstrate all his capabilities in his homeland. Even the question of happiness is often closely related to the concept of homeland. Because the motherland, every handful of its soil is the legacy left to us by our ancestors. Homeland is the holy soil where human blood was shed, a blessed place that perfects it and gives meaning to its life. Homeland is the greatest and most priceless inheritance left from ancestors to generations, the ground where the ashes of our grandfathers and grandmothers, fathers and mothers are laid, and the soil where each of us will lay our heads in time. This is how father and mother always explain and emphasize this fact to their children in the family

Loyalty to the motherland and the feeling of patriotism should be firmly established in their minds and hearts. For every nation, the Motherland is a territory determined by fate and historically endowed. A person with a homeland has high pride and clear goals. He can withstand any tests of life. Even the animals crawling in the desert, the birds flying in the air, and the fish in the seas and rivers feel and protect themselves. The sense of homeland is to love, respect, value and acknowledge one's people.

The happiness of every person living in our independent country is directly related to the development of our Motherland. For this reason, it is necessary to spend all knowledge, strength and potential for the development of the Motherland as a sacred duty of all citizens living in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The development of the country, first of all, depends on the maturity of its children. This is reflected in the fact that each of our compatriots feels responsible for their spiritual development, lives in harmony with the interests of this country and people.

Patriotism is a set of social, spiritual and moral qualities that express a person's love for the land where he was born and grew up. Today, the task of forming a sense of military patriotism has become an urgent issue. Because, under the guise of "mass culture", "cosmopolitanism", that is, ideas calling for renouncing national traditions and culture, patriotism, and non-patriotism, are spreading widely among young people.

The main sign of military patriotism is self-sacrifice, and its highest form is courage. This dedication and courage is reflected in the spiritual heritage of our people and in the image of our ancestors. Folk proverbs, proverbs, fairy tales, legends and epics call us to goodness, bravery, honesty, correctness and purity as well as to love the Motherland and be loyal to our people.

Alpomish, a masterpiece of our epics, is a heroic song of our ancestors that expresses the identity of our nation and has served to strengthen the will of the defenders of the homeland for centuries. Therefore, it is necessary to teach the spiritual heritage of our ancestors, as well as the bravery of our ancestors like Shiroq, Spitamen, Najmuddin Kubro, Jaloliddin Manguberdi, who sacrificed their lives for the freedom of the Motherland, as a bright expression of our people's boundless love for the Motherland.

The feeling of the Motherland and patriotism were very important for our great grandfathers like al-Khorazmi, al-Farghani, al-Farobi, al-Beruni, who contributed to the development of world science and culture. For this reason, they always recorded their names with the name of the country where they were born and grew up, and were known to the world as Bukharis, Termizis, Samarkandis, Shoshis, Khorezmids, Nasafis, Farghanis, Margilanis.

Therefore, the spiritual heritage of our ancestors, the way of life, the narratives and stories about them all serve as an important source for educating the young generation in the military-patriotic spirit. It is desirable to study these sources in the family circle, to use them widely as examples. Summing up on the basis of the above points, it is worth noting that the educational importance of the family in forming a sense of military patriotism in young people is extremely incomparable. To use it effectively:

1. Always keep in mind that the family is the initial and main link of society, which is responsible for preparing children for life;

2. To widely promote that the parents have a great responsibility for the mental, physical and moral education of the child, especially for the formation of a sense of patriotism;

3. To explain in detail to children and young people that military patriotism is the guarantee of the independence and development of our country;

4. In the process of family upbringing, paying special attention to the formation of military-patriotic feeling and wide use of the possibilities of our national spiritual heritage;

5. It is necessary to widen the joint cooperation of the family, military educational institutions and neighborhood community in the path of human development. Family upbringing is the main factor in the formation of military

patriotism, and its possibilities are immeasurable. Military patriotism is the protection of the interests of society and the sovereignty of the state.

Therefore, military patriotism is a special type and an integral part of national and national patriotism, which becomes more important in the conditions when Uzbekistan has achieved national and state independence. Educating the growing generation in the spirit of military patriotism is the formation of a sense of loyalty to the Motherland in children and young people, regardless of nationality, language, religion, and gender, and serves to educate them as individuals capable of fulfilling their civic duties and constitutional obligations, protecting the interests of society and the state.

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